

***In silico* screening of anti-inflammatory activity of phytochemicals from *Adhatoda vasica* as potential inhibitors against ARDS: Molecular docking and MD simulation**

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Abstract

Background: ARDS (Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome) is characterized by the rapid onset of non-cardiogenic pulmonary edema and impaired gas exchange, primarily due to a severe inflammatory response, which is often referred to as a cytokine storm. As inflammation pathways can be the major target to deal with ARDS, current study demonstrates the molecular docking of phytochemicals derived from *Adhatoda vasica* against the three different proteins in the pro-inflammatory cytokines cascade - IL8 receptor - CXCR1, MPO, and TLR4. The study investigates the possibility of targeting and inhibiting these proteins via selected phytochemicals from *Adhatoda vasica* to circumvent lung inflammation.

Materials and methods: Eleven bioactive compounds from AV were pharmacologically analyzed using Protovx II and Swiss ADME. They were further docked with CXCR1, MPO and TLR4 separately, using the docking software AutoDock Vina and compared with the anti-inflammatory standard drugs. The complexes showing best binding affinities were taken up further for molecular dynamic simulation investigation to assess the time-dependent stability of the complexes.

Results: *In silico*, ADMET properties prediction shows that quercetin and vasicine indicated adequate values for solubility and absorption characteristics with minimal toxic effects. In docking, Vasicine showed the most favorable binding energy towards the receptor CXCR1 while, for the other two targets: TLR4 and MPO, the best binding affinity was obtained for quercetin. MD simulation demonstrated stable binding between the aforesaid three complexes of proteins and phytochemicals.

Conclusions: The study suggests that quercetin and vasicine could be promising alternatives to commonly used synthetic drugs for the treatment of ARDS. These compounds may offer potential for reduced side effects while effectively targeting the inflammatory pathways involved in the condition.

Keywords: ARDS; Proteins; Pro-inflammatory cytokines; Docking; Bioactive compounds

1. Introduction

Characteristic features of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) include increased permeability of pulmonary capillary endothelial cells and alveolar epithelial cells, which leads to hypoxemia. (Koh, 2014). It is a life-risking form of acute respiratory failure with subsequent multiple organ system failure (Maca et al., 2017). In ARDS, various fluids and proteins are leaked to the interstitium due to the increased permeability of the capillaries. Subsequently, the injured epithelial cells allow fluids, neutrophils, and RBCs to enter the alveolar space. Alveolar and interstitial edema are typically observed during the exudative stage of ARDS. This further leads to inflammation and can subsequently lead to the development of various severe conditions, including lung sepsis, pneumonia, and pancreatitis, affecting not only the lungs but also other body organs. These inflammatory pathways are triggered by damage to the lungs resulting from trauma, infection, or other inflammatory conditions (Matthay et al., 2002). In response to the inflammation, both the adaptive and innate immune systems become activated. Innate immune system involves certain enzymes like MPO, various receptors like: CXCR1 and TLR4 receptors. TLR4

receptors are responsible for recognizing microbial patterns and initiating various signaling pathways, including MAPK and NF- κ B (Mogensen and Paludan, 2005; Aboudounya and Heads, 2021). In general, inflammation serves a protective role by promoting pathogen clearance and facilitating tissue repair. In contrast, excessive inflammation can lead to alveolar damage, characterized by increased epithelial and endothelial permeability. This results in the accumulation of protein-rich fluid in the alveoli (Ashbaugh et al., 1967).

Authors have selected the aforementioned three protein markers for the present study: CXCL-8, TLR4, and MPO to be targeted. The first protein, CXCR1/CXCL-8, is a receptor for Interleukin-8 (IL-8) and is a potent neutrophil chemotactic factor (Baggiolini et al., 1995). It activates neutrophils through chemotaxis, which is a key component of the inflammatory response. IL-8 binds to its cognate G-protein-coupled CXC chemokine receptors, CXCR1 and CXCR2 and as a result the entire cascade of phosphorylation gets activated (Cesta, et al., 2024). This activation subsequently triggers MAPK and protein kinase C (PKC) pathways through the upregulation of the NLRP3 inflammasome and NF- κ B activity, which further exacerbates lung inflammation in ARDS. (Stillie et al., 2009; Holmes et al., 1991; Huang, et al., 2024).

The second protein target, TLR4, is a member of the innate immune receptor family found on the surface of various immune cells. Its key function is to activate signal transduction through both MyD88-dependent and MyD88-independent pathways. TLR4 generates many proinflammatory cytokines important for innate and adaptive immunity. The classical MyD88-dependent signaling pathway primarily mediates the transcription of NF- κ B and the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, initiating downstream inflammatory responses. (Yang, et al., 2018). It recognizes exogenous and endogenous ligands from the pathogens known as Damage-Associated Molecular Pattern Molecules (DAMPs) and Pathogen-Associated Molecular Pattern molecules (PAMPs) (Kawasaki and Kawai, 2014; Molteni et al., 2016). Once it recognizes PAMPs (pathogen-associated molecular patterns) or DAMPs (damage-associated molecular patterns), the innate immune response is activated, leading to inflammation (Kuzmich et al., 2017). Both alveolar macrophages and alveolar epithelial cells have TLR4 on their surface. TLR4 identifies significant ligands such as: heat shock protein, hyaluronan, and LPS during the progression of ARDS (Bagheri, et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2016). When the activated TLR intracellular domain (TIR) binds to MyD88, it recruits IL-1 receptor-associated kinase (IRAK). This interaction results in the autophosphorylation of IRAK, which then binds to Tumor Necrosis Factor Receptor-Associated Factor 6 (TRAF6). This binding activates TRAF6, leading to the activation of Activator Protein-1 (AP-1) and Nuclear Factor kappa B (NF- κ B). Consequently, this activation triggers the expression and release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-1, IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and various chemokines. (Lu, et al., 2022).

The third protein chosen, Myeloperoxidase (MPO) is involved in generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) for antimicrobial activities in various pathological conditions. It is a heme-containing peroxidase, and is expressed in activated neutrophils (Le Marchand et al., 2000). Neutrophils are recruited to the lungs in large numbers in response to various lung injuries, infections, ozone inhalation, and to the presence of tobacco smoke particles (Le Marchand et al, 2000; Schmekel et al., 1990; Hunninghake et al., 1979; Petruska et al., 1991; Schmekel et al., 1990). Similarly, large numbers of neutrophils are recruited during the early inflammatory phase of ARDS, and the damaged pulmonary capillary endothelial cells get attached to these neutrophils, resulting in the release of inflammatory mediators. During the early stages of ARDS, MPO is produced from the activated neutrophils that get attached to the surface of endothelial cells, inducing inflammation (Ren, et al., 2022). Based on the above mechanisms, TLR4, CXCR1, and MPO are considered key targets for inhibition in the present study, aiming to control inflammation and manage ARDS effectively.

Further, 11 phytochemicals from the plant *Adhatoda vasica* (AV) are chosen for the present study. AV is well-regarded in traditional Indian medicine for its use in managing respiratory disorders like colds, coughs, nasal congestion, bronchitis, upper respiratory infections, and asthma. It is a member of the Acanthaceae family and is called by several common names, including Baker, Malabar Nut, and Vasaka (Rudrapal et al., 2023). According to

existing literature, it has been demonstrated that the AV possesses anti-inflammatory properties. It has been shown that administering AV extract reduces lung damage, thrombosis, and fibrosis by modifying the cellular hypoxic response and the inflammation-thrombosis axis (Gheware et al., 2021). Basit et al. (2022) revealed that AV can decrease in the acute inflammatory pain caused by formalin and carrageenan. A study has provided the first clinical evidence showing that AV herbal extract therapy leads to a reduction in HIF-1 levels in COVID-19 patients which is a major activator of SARS-CoV-2 infection and inflammatory response (Verma et al., 2023).

This medicinal plant possesses various phytochemical compounds, including alkaloids, polyphenols, and flavonoids, known to be anti-inflammatory in nature (Gonfa, et al., 2023). AV has many medicinally active ingredients such as, vasicine, deoxyvasicinone, vasicinolone, vasicinol, vasicinone, quercetin, gallic acid, ferulic acid, catechin, vanillic acid, p-cumaric acid (Shoaib, 2022; Basit, et al.,2022). Among these, quercetin is a flavonoid with potential chemopreventive effects. It exerts anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic actions by inhibiting the cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase pathways, constraining the production of pro-inflammatory substances. (Jafarina et al., 2020). Vasicine, deoxyvasicinone, vasicinolone, vasicinol, and vasicinone belong to the alkaloid group. Several studies have indicated that they possess anti-inflammatory, cytoprotective, and hepatoprotective potential (Ghanta, et al., 2022). Catechin, Ferulic acid, Gallic acid, p-cumaric acid, and Vanillic acid belong to the family of polyphenolic acid. These polyphenols can modulate the expression of various pro-inflammatory markers such as nitric oxide (NO) synthases, lipoxygenase, cyclooxygenase, and multiple other cytokines (Yahfoufi, et al., 2018).

Among these mentioned above, 11 phytocompounds from AV are chosen to analyze their interactions with the above-mentioned three proteins, using molecular docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulation in the present study. Reparixin, Resatorvid, and Berberine, the known inhibitors of the proteins CXCR1, TLR4, and MPO, respectively, have been used as standards to validate the docking results.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental process

The methodology involved in the present study starts from meticulous selection and preparation of protein targets and ligands mentioned in the above section. This process was followed by ADMET profiling of the ligands and the execution of molecular docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. The 3-D structures of the target proteins and ligands were identified and retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (RCSB-PDB) and PubChem databases, respectively. ADME profiling was conducted using SwissADME (version 4), and toxicity predictions were made with Protox II software (version 2.7). Molecular docking studies were performed using the web-based AutoDock-Vina program (version 1.5.7). The results from the docking studies were then utilized to conduct MD simulations, providing a deeper understanding of the dynamic characteristics of each binding site.

2.2. Ligand and receptor preparation

The 3-D structures of TLR4 (PDB ID: 3FXI), MPO (PDB ID: 1MYP), and CXCR1 (PDB ID: 2LNL) were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB). These protein structures were prepared for docking using PMV software, which included the removal of water molecules, the addition of polar hydrogen atoms, and the assignment of Kollman charges. The prepared protein structures were then saved in PDBQT format.

Aforementioned a detailed survey of the literature was conducted to identify the most effective anti-inflammatory phytocompounds from AV, including vasicine, deoxyvasicinone, vasicinolone, vasicinol, vasicinone, quercetin, gallic acid, ferulic acid, catechin, vanillic acid, and p-cumaric acid (Shoaib, 2022; Basit et al., 2022). The three-dimensional structures of these 11 phytocompounds were obtained from the PubChem database in SDF format. In addition to these phytocompounds, 3 anti-inflammatory drugs (one for each relevant protein, namely

TLR4, MPO, and CXCR1) were obtained and used as anti-inflammatory drug compounds. The files were converted to PDBQT format using PMV software for subsequent *in silico* analysis. The molecular formula, PubChem CID, and 2D structure of the selected phytochemicals, along with the anti-inflammatory standard drugs, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Molecular formula, PubChem CID, and 2D structure of phytochemicals along with anti-inflammatory drugs

Ligand name	PubChem CID	Molecular formula	2D structure
Quercetin	5280343	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	
Vasicine	667496	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	
Deoxyvasicinone	68261	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	
Vasicinolone	158720	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃	
Vasicinol	442934	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	
Vasicinone	442935	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	

Gallic acid	370	$C_7H_6O_5$	
Ferulic acid	445858	$C_{10}H_{10}O_4$	
Catechin	9064	$C_{15}H_{14}O_6$	
Vanillic acid	8468	$C_8H_8O_4$	
p-cumaric acid	637542	$C_9H_8O_3$	

Apremilast (Standard)	11561674	$C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_7S$	
Reparixin (Standard)	9838712	$C_{14}H_{21}NO_3S$	
Resatorvid (Standard)	11703255	$C_{15}H_{17}ClFNO_4S$	

2.3. Active site identification

The active sites of the proteins were identified from the castP online tool, which were marked in the AutoDock tool to draw a grid box. The active site residues were identified and marked to define the grid box, with a spacing of 0.375 Å (Kar et al., 2022)

- For TLR4, a grid box of dimensions 88 × 106 × 126 Å was centered at coordinates (1.586, 0.052, -4.38).
- For CXCR1, the grid box measured 52 × 66 × 70 Å centered at coordinates (11.838, -35.979, -12.889).
- MPO's active site was enclosed in a grid box of dimensions 118 × 80 × 66 Å centered at coordinates (26.167, -4.833, -1.056).

2.4. ADMET studies of selected phytochemicals

ADMET stands for Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity. It describes the pharmacokinetics profile of a drug which is essential for determining its pharmacodynamic properties (Srivastava et

al., 2022). The ADME analysis was performed using SwissADME software, while toxicity was assessed using Protox-II (Shrestha, 2022; Han et al., 2019).

2.5. Molecular docking and visualization

A molecular docking study was carried out using AutoDock Vina Software, and the BIOVIA discovery studio was used to visualize ligand-protein interactions. The selected phytochemicals obtained from the PubChem were docked to the proteins (receptors). The prepared proteins saved in PDBQT form were separately integrated into the AutoDock tool. To manage computational resources during docking experiments, the Exhaustiveness parameter in AutoDock Vina was default set by the software (Forli et al., 2016). Docking runs were conducted with a standard exhaustiveness level of 8 for all sets (Swargiary & Mani, 2022). Redocking of phytochemicals with proteins was performed to validate initial docking results.

2.6. Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulation

Following the molecular docking analysis, the structure of protein-ligand complex was studied using MD Simulation Software "Desmond V12 Schrodinger" for 100 nanoseconds time duration (Ranimol, 2022). MD is a computational technique used to simulate the dynamic behavior of atoms and molecules, precisely their flexibility and stability. Biologists commonly use MD simulation to study the stability and complexity of protein-protein or protein-ligand interactions (Al-Dhuayan, 2023).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. ADMET analysis

ADME-T-based drug screening is a critical phase in drug development for determining the bioavailability and toxicity of selected phytochemicals. Phytochemicals that pass the ADMET profile can be considered safe and potential drug candidates with minimal toxicity (Azeem et al., 2022). The prediction of the drug likeness of the phytochemicals was carried out using SwissADME and protox II to analyse their drug-like characteristics and assess their pharmacokinetic properties.

The SwissADME analysis (Table 2) of all the 11 phytochemicals and the 3 anti-inflammatory standard drugs demonstrated that all compounds exhibit significant drug-like properties without violating Lipinski's criteria. According to "Lipinski's rule of five," a molecule is likely to be absorbed or penetrate biological membranes if it meets the following criteria: (i) molecular weight of 500 Daltons or less, (ii) not more than 5 hydrogen bond donors, (iii) not more than 10 hydrogen bond acceptors, (iv) octanol-water partition coefficient (Log P) of 5 or less, and (v) topological polar surface area (TPSA) less than 140 Å² (Abdullahi et al., 2022). TPSA is a critical factor for optimal drug absorption (Matondo et al., 2022). In accordance with these criteria, the molecular weights of these phytochemicals and anti-inflammatory standard drugs range from 160 to 460 g/mol. They have 0 to 5 hydrogen bond donors and 1 to 7 hydrogen bond acceptors. The Log P values for these compounds range from 0 to 3, and the TPSA values are ranging from 15 to 130 Å, indicating their suitability and safety for use as drugs (Matondo, et al., 2022).

Table 2: Drug-likeness prediction of compounds using SwissADME

Ligands	Molecular weight (g/mol)	No. of hydrogen bond acceptor	No. of hydrogen bond donor	Log P	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski rule
Quercetin	302.24	7	5	1.63	131.36	Yes
Vasicine	188.23	2	1	1.64	35.83	Yes
Deoxyvasicinone	186.21	2	0	2.09	34.89	Yes
Vasicinolone	218.21	4	2	1.52	75.35	Yes
Vasicinol	204.23	3	2	1.40	56.06	Yes
Vasicinone	202.21	3	1	1.67	55.12	Yes
Gallic acid	170.12	5	4	0.21	97.99	Yes
Ferulic acid	194.18	4	2	1.62	66.76	Yes
Catechin	290.27	6	5	1.47	110.38	Yes
Vasicoline	291.39	1	0	2.94	18.54	Yes
Vanillic acid	168.15	4	2	1.40	66.76	Yes
p-cumaric acid	164.16	3	2	0.95	57.53	Yes
Reparixin	283.39	3	1	2.38	71.62	Yes
Resatorvid	361.82	5	1	2.63	80.85	Yes
Apremilast	460.50	7	1	3.02	127.46	Yes

Table 3 summarizes the key ADME parameters (gastrointestinal absorption, blood-brain-barrier, metabolism and bioavailability score) related to the pharmacokinetic behaviour of the tested compounds. Among these parameters Gastrointestinal (GI) absorption is a crucial factor, especially for orally administered drugs. All phytocompounds and the anti-inflammatory standard drugs are expected to exhibit rapid gastrointestinal absorption. One other parameter studied for these compounds is permeability of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) which indicates whether a compound can affect the brain, either positively or negatively. Mostly conventional anticancer drugs are known to potentially harm brain neurons during their transit across the BBB, leading to severe neurological outcomes. Among the tested compounds, six phytocompounds and reparixin showed positive BBB permeability values, indicating their potential to cross the BBB. In contrast, the remaining phytocompounds and anti-inflammatory standard drugs (resatorvid and apremilast) displayed negative BBB permeability values, suggesting that these substances are unlikely to penetrate the BBB and, therefore, should not induce neurotoxicity in the brain.

Table 3: ADME predictions of compounds using SwissADME

Ligands	GI	BBB	CYP2D6	CYP3A4	Bioavailability Score
Quercetin	High	No	Yes	Yes	0.55
Vasicine	High	No	No	No	0.55
Deoxyvasicinone	High	Yes	No	No	0.55
Vasicinolone	High	No	No	No	0.55
Vasicinol	High	No	No	No	0.55
Vasicinone	High	No	No	No	0.55
Gallic acid	High	No	No	Yes	0.55
Ferulic acid	High	Yes	No	No	0.85

Catechin	High	No	No	No	0.55
Vasicoline	High	Yes	Yes	Yes	0.55
Vanillic acid	High	No	No	No	0.85
p-cumaric acid	High	Yes	No	No	0.85
Reparixin	High	Yes	No	No	0.55
Resatorvid	High	No	No	Yes	0.55
Apremilast	High	No	Yes	Yes	0.55

Drugs once internalized, get metabolized which involves various processes such as hydration, isomerization, hydrolysis, conjugation, oxidoreduction, reduction, and condensation, all of these ultimately aimed at facilitating the drug excretion. While metabolic enzymes are present in many organs, the liver contains the highest concentration. Drug metabolism is primarily regulated by cytochrome enzymes CYP2D6 and CYP3A4. These are responsible for metabolizing many drugs (Elbouzidi et al., 2023). In the present study quercetin, gallic acid, vasicoline, resatorvid, and apremilast are identified as inhibitors of these cytochrome enzymes which indicates that it will be difficult to metabolize these drugs in the human body.

For optimal absorption and distribution, a bioavailability score of 0.55 or higher is desirable. The bioavailability scores for all the phytochemicals and anti-inflammatory standard drugs were found to be 0.55 or 0.85 (for vanillic acid, ferulic acid, and p-coumaric acid), indicating that these phytochemicals likely have good tissue absorption and distribution profiles.

Further, ProTox-II was employed to estimate the toxicity of the compounds by calculating their median lethal dosage (LD_{50}) values and assigning them to specific toxicity classes. The classification of protox II class indicates that these compounds exhibit a low level of toxicity when administered, as per the Globally Harmonized System: (<https://tox.charite.de/protox3/>)

Class I: fatal if swallowed ($LD_{50} \leq 5$), Class II: fatal if swallowed ($5 < LD_{50} \leq 50$), Class III: toxic if swallowed ($50 < LD_{50} \leq 300$), Class IV: harmful if swallowed ($300 < LD_{50} \leq 2000$), Class V: may be harmful if swallowed ($2000 < LD_{50} \leq 5000$), Class VI: non-toxic ($LD_{50} > 5000$)

Table 4: Toxicity prediction of compounds using Protox-II

Ligands	Toxicity					Toxicity class	LD_{50}
	Hepato	Carcino	Immuno	Mutagen	Cyto		
Quercetin	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	3	159
Vasicine	No	No	No	No	No	3	290
Deoxyvasicinone	No	No	No	No	No	4	1100
Vasicinolone	No	No	No	No	No	4	1250
Vasicinol	No	No	No	No	No	3	100
Vasicinone	No	No	No	No	No	4	1100
Gallic acid	No	Yes	No	No	No	4	2000

Ferulic acid	No	No	Yes	No	No	4	1772
Catechin	No	No	No	No	No	6	10000
Vasicoline	No	No	No	No	No	3	290
Vanillic acid	No	No	No	No	No	4	2000
p-cumaric acid	No	Yes	No	No	No	5	2850
Reparixin	No	No	No	No	No	4	1540
Resatorvid	No	No	No	No	No	4	2000
Apremilast	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	6	12000

Table 4 displays the LD₅₀ values and toxicity classes of the 11 phytochemicals and anti-inflammatory standard drugs. The organ toxicity prediction results revealed that out of the all compounds tested, 10 compounds (vasicine, deoxyvasicinone, vasicinolone, vasicinol, vasicinone, catechin, vasicoline, vanillic acid, reparixin, and resatorvid) did not exhibit any toxicity. However, quercetin, gallic acid, and p-coumaric acid were found to possess carcinogenic properties, while ferulic acid and apremilast were identified as having immunogenic properties. Additionally, quercetin demonstrated mutagenic properties, and apremilast exhibited cytotoxic effects. Despite these findings, the toxicity data suggests that all phytochemicals tested have potential as promising drug candidates, as supported by the ADMET prediction analysis (Degfie et al., 2022). All estimated toxicity values, expressed as LD₅₀, are categorized as class 3 or higher which can be considered to possess minimal toxicity.

It is important to note that the therapeutic profile presented here pertains solely to oral administration. The druggability of these compounds (such as quercetin, p-cumaric acid, ferulic acid) can be enhanced through various galenic formulations (e.g., solutions, tablets, and capsules etc.) and choosing an alternative administration route (e.g., parenteral, intravenous and inhalation etc.). A drug's absorption is influenced by its physicochemical properties as well as these factors (Matondo et al., 2022).

3.2. Molecular docking and visualization of protein-ligand interactions

The aforementioned 11 phytochemicals and three anti-inflammatory standard drugs were selected for molecular docking with the proteins important in ARDS. The primary parameter analyzed during this process was binding energy, which provides insight into the strength and affinity of the ligand-protein interactions. A lower binding energy indicates a stronger interaction between the ligand and the protein (Meng et al., 2011 (Table 5).

Table 5: Ligand-protein binding energies

S. No.	Ligands	Binding energy (kcal/mol)		
		MPO	TLR4	CXCR1
1.	Berberine (Standard Drug)	-7.8	-	-
2.	Reparixin (Standard Drug)	-	-	-6.2
3.	Resatorvid (Standard Drug)	-	-7.1	-

4.	Quercetin	-9.4	-7.8	-7.0
5.	Vasicine	-7.9	-7.0	-7.7
6.	Deoxyvasicinone	-6.9	-6.3	-6.0
7.	Vasicinolone	-7.2	-6.3	-6.2
8.	Vasicinol	-7.3	-6.0	-5.8
9.	Vasicinone	-7.0	-6.5	-5.9
10.	Gallic acid	-6.8	-6.1	-6.2
11.	Ferulic acid	-6.8	-6.0	-6.0
12.	Catechin	-8.2	-7.4	-7.0
13.	Vanillic acid	-6.5	-5.4	-5.7
14.	p-cumaric acid	-7.0	-6.1	-6.6

Protein-ligand interaction visualizes the bond formation between the ligand and receptor. This online software was used to visualize interactions between molecules, such as hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions. Hydrogen bonds are known to significantly enhance the strength of protein-ligand interactions by displacing water molecules from the protein's binding site into the surrounding solvent, as noted by Kar et al. (2022). Hydrophobic interactions also play a crucial role in increasing binding affinity at drug-target interfaces. The presence of water molecules in hydrophobic regions introduces flexibility, and there is potential to engineer the drug, the protein, or their interface to further increase binding affinity. Moreover, increasing the number of hydrophobic atoms in the active core of the drug-protein interface can enhance the biological activity of the drug, as suggested by Patil et al. (2010).

During the study, the binding energies were found to be in the range of -9.4 to -6.5 kcal/mol in the case of protein MPO and the ligands whereas, for TLR4 protein it was observed to be in the range of -7.8 to -5.4 kcal/mol. Similarly, for protein CXCR1, the binding energy ranged from -7.7 to -5.7 kcal/mol.

For MPO protein, quercetin demonstrated the strongest interaction with the, achieving a binding energy of -9.4 kcal/mol, followed by catechin with -8.2 kcal/mol. All other phytochemicals exhibited binding affinities higher than the anti-inflammatory standard drug, berberine, which had a binding energy of -7.8 kcal/mol. The binding interaction between MPO and quercetin is shown in Figure 1. Quercetin formed hydrogen bonds at Gln 91 and Arg 239, hydrophobic interactions at Arg 333, Gly 335, Tyr 334, His 336, Phe 332, Met 87, and electrostatic interactions at Asp 94 and His 336 (see Table 6).

Figure 1: Binding interaction between MPO and quercetin

For TLR4, quercetin again showed the best interaction, with a binding energy of -7.8 kcal/mol, followed by catechin at -7.4 kcal/mol. Other phytochemicals had higher binding energies compared to the anti-inflammatory standard drug resatorvid, which was -7.1 kcal/mol. The binding interaction of TLR4 and quercetin is shown in Figure 2. Quercetin formed 2 types of bonds, hydrogen bonds at Ser 127 and Tyr 131, and hydrophobic interactions at Val 82, Ile 80, and Tyr 131.

Figure 2. Binding interaction between TLR4 and quercetin

In the case of CXCR1, vasicine achieved the best binding energy of -7.7 kcal/mol, followed by quercetin and catechin, both at -7.0 kcal/mol. Other phytochemicals showed higher binding affinities than the anti-inflammatory standard drug reparixin, which had a binding energy of -6.2 kcal/mol. The binding interaction between CXCR1 and vasicine is shown in Figure 3. Vasicine formed hydrogen bonds at Phe 121 and Asn 120, and hydrophobic interactions at Leu 252, Trp 255, and Val 248.

Figure 3. Binding interaction between CXCR1 and vasicine

Table 6: Different bonding interactions of three best docked complexes

Complex	Residue	Interaction Type	Distance (nm)
MPO-Quercetin	Arg 333	Pi-Sulfur	5.20
	Tyr 334	Amide Pi-stacked	5.84
		Pi-Pi T shaped	5.84
	Gly 335	Pi-Sigma	3.73
	His 336	Pi-Pi T shaped	4.62
		Pi Cation	3.78
	Asp 94	Pi-Anion	3.28
	Gln 91	Hydrogen bond	2.31
Met 87	Pi-Sulfur	5.83	

	Phe 332	Pi-Pi T shaped	5.77
	Gly 335	Pi-Sigma	3.73
	Arg 239	Hydrogen bond	2.35
TLR4-Quercetin	Ser 127	Hydrogen bond	2.33
	Tyr 131	Hydrogen bond	3.99
		Pi-Pi Stacked	5.51
	Val 82	Pi-Alkyl	4.68
	Ile 80	Pi-Sigma	3.71
Pi-Alkyl		4.88	
CXCR1-vasicine	Phe 121	Hydrogen bond	2.76
	Val 248	Alkyl	4.65
	Trp 255	Pi-Pi T shaped	4.73
	Leu 252	Pi-Sigma	3.78
	Asn 120	Hydrogen bond	2.64

These three docked complexes (MPO-quercetin, TLR4-quercetin and CXCR1-vasicine) were further subjected to MD simulation to assess their stability.

3.4. MD simulation

MDS's are applied to investigate the stability of the protein and ligand during their interaction simulation (Samreen, et al., 2023). In order to do this, a number of parameters, including RMSD, H-bonds, and radius of gyration, are calculated and analysed. The dynamic aspects of the docking complex involving the top compounds MPO-quercetin, TLR4-quercetin and CXCR1-vasicine were simulated for 100 ns to understand the structural stability of ligand and protein during their interaction.

The RMSD plots obtained illustrate the progression of protein structural deviation (left Y-axis), where all protein frames were aligned to the reference backbone, and RMSD was computed based on selected atoms. Tracking protein RMSD throughout the simulation offers valuable insights into its conformational stability. A stabilized RMSD towards the end of the simulation suggests that the system has reached equilibrium, with fluctuations centering around a consistent average structure. The ligand RMSD (right Y-axis) reflects the ligand's stability within the binding pocket relative to the protein. The plot labeled 'Lig fit Prot' displays the RMSD of the ligand after aligning the protein-ligand complex to the protein backbone of the reference structure, followed by measuring the RMSD of the ligand's heavy atoms.

The protein-ligand complex MPO-quercetin became stable from around 30ns with an average RMSD of 2.4Å and 2.8, respectively as shown in the Figure 4A. The docked complex TLR4-quercetin exhibited variations in the 70ns but remained nearly stable with an average RMSD of 3.6Å and 2.4Å, respectively (Figure 4B). The protein-ligand complex CXCR1-vasicine showed little fluctuations till the first 40ns, after that the system had become almost stable with an average RMSD -7Å and 4Å respectively (Fig. 4C) The results indicated the stable dynamic behaviour of all the complexes with time.

Figure 4: RMSD of protein-ligand over the time scale of 100 ns (A) RMSD plot of MPO and quercetin (B) RMSD plot of TLR4 and quercetin (C) RMSD plot of CXCR1 and vasicine

As it is observed from Figure 4A the MPO-quercetin complex exhibited strong and stable interactions throughout the simulation. The structures of the MPO-quercetin complex maintained a consistent interaction pattern with minimal deviations, indicating stability during most of the simulation. Analyzing stable ligand-protein interactions and identifying key residues involved in ligand binding within the pocket is crucial for detecting binding hotspots. Hydrogen bonds are particularly important for ligand binding, as they significantly impact drug selectivity, metabolism, and absorption. These properties must be carefully considered when designing new drugs. The Table 7 below details the hydrogen bonds present in the protein-ligand complexes.

The radius of gyration (RoG) measures the compactness of the system, with a stable RoG graph indicating the conformational stability of the complex during MD simulations. Among the three protein-ligand complexes, TLR4-quercetin exhibited the highest structural stability, maintaining an average compact radius of 3.80 Å (Figure 5.).

Figure 5. Radius of gyration of top three docked complexes over the time scale of 100 ns.

The MPO-quercetin complex also showed structural stability, with an average compact radius of 3.78 Å. In comparison, the CXCR1-vasicine complex maintained stability with an average compact radius of 2.72 Å. A consistent RoG value signifies a stable, folded complex structure, while variations in RoG over time may suggest misfolding. Higher RoG values are typically associated with greater conformational flexibility (Gao, et al., 2023).

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the promising anti-inflammatory potential of *Adhatoda vasica* (AV) and its major phytoconstituents in managing inflammatory conditions associated with ARDS. All the phytoconstituents exhibited favorable properties during *in silico* screening, including drug-likeness, ADMET profiles, and strong docking affinities with target proteins. Among the tested phytoconstituents, vasicine and quercetin were shortlisted due to their superior binding affinities compared to standard anti-inflammatory drugs. Docking studies revealed that quercetin and vasicine exhibited strong binding energies with key target proteins, including MPO, TLR4, and CXCR1, indicating their potential to inhibit pro-inflammatory pathways. These two compounds were further subjected to molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with their respective receptors. The MD simulations of the protein-ligand complexes (MPO-quercetin, TLR4-quercetin, and CXCR1-vasicine) demonstrated stable and promising interactions throughout the 100 ns simulation period. The findings suggest that quercetin and vasicine may possess significant immunomodulatory therapeutic potential against ARDS by effectively inhibiting pro-inflammatory proteins. However, further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are necessary to validate their anti-inflammatory efficacy and therapeutic potential.

Acknowledgment

The authors acknowledge the Department of Biotechnology of Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida for providing suitable infrastructure to complete the project.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing interests that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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